

MODERN METHODS AND APPROACHES USED IN PROMOTING
FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Distance learning in the social sciences and humanities

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Abstract. In this article, motivation is considered as one of the main factors determining the success of learning a foreign language. Different ways to increase motivation in a foreign language lesson are considered at school.

Key words: motivation, foreign language, teacher, lesson, pupil, student, school, motivation, method.

Nowadays, the need of the times requires learning foreign languages. Because knowing a foreign language opens wide doors of opportunities, and it is also considered one of the main factors in developing the personality of students capable of intercultural communication. But the quality of achieving the goal depends, first of all, on the motivation and needs of the person, his interests.

It is encouragement and motivation that creates goal-oriented activity, helps to choose the most effective tools and methods in language learning, and to determine their order to achieve the goal.

Success in mastering the English language depends on the teacher's teaching methods and the ability to use modern technologies in the process of solving educational problems. The ever-increasing volume of scientific information requires the teacher to search for new and more effective teaching techniques and methods that allow to provide more information in a certain unit of educational time. These teaching techniques and methods should make the lesson open, emotional and lively, so that the information is better absorbed and remembered by students.

Some of the most effective ways to motivate students in foreign language classes are:

"Work in pairs" or "work in groups"

Proper use of "pair work" or "group work" is one of the most successful ways to increase students' interest. A language can be learned better through close cooperation and communication between students. This type of collaboration will undoubtedly benefit all or both students. In fact, students can write dialogues, interviews, draw and comment on pictures, role play, etc. they can help each other in working on different types of assignments.

Research on foreign language acquisition has shown that students differ in their acquisition of skills. One student may be good at writing while another may be good at

speaking; a third reader might be good at role-playing games, etc. In addition, some students find it more convenient to learn language rules from their classmates than from their teacher. Language learning requires teamwork and mutual trust, which "pair" or "group work" can provide.

Rearranging the seating arrangement of students

The way children sit in the classroom often determines the dynamics of the lesson. Because simply changing the seating arrangement can make a remarkable difference in the cohesion of a group of students, and there are many cases where the seating arrangement is the deciding factor in the success or failure of a class. But in some cases, the seating plan you use may not be completely under your control—for example, if the desks are nailed to the floor, or if the school has strict rules about moving furniture. Each teacher has their own preference for sitting in the classroom. One of the best options for large classes is to arrange the tables in a U shape. But whatever seating model the teacher chooses, the classroom will be most comfortable if the following principles are taken into account:

a) Maximize eye contact.

If the responding student does not make eye contact with others, attention to his performance is reduced.

b) Ensuring that students sit at a comfortable distance from each other.

The teacher must make sure that there are no students who are alone. Also, try not to leave too much space between students.

Error correction

When the teacher points out every mistake, the students are very afraid of making mistakes. Consequently, children are very reluctant to participate in communication because they are too prone to make mistakes. Thus, teachers need to know when and how to correct mistakes without hurting the child's feelings. Regarding how to correct errors, there are several techniques that the teacher should choose depending on the type of error. Among these methods, we can distinguish the following: self-correction, correction by other students and teacher's correction.

Role play

This is one of the most effective ways to increase students' interest in the lesson. Teachers are recommended to use role-playing games to help passive students participate in the lesson, because in the process of playing, they overcome their inhibitions and anxieties. In addition, role-playing games are included in all textbooks and language learning tools. Examples: a game of hide-and-seek or guessing, a fake conversation between a buyer and a seller, a conversation between a doctor and a patient, etc.

Use of audiovisual means.

Modern schools are equipped with various audio-visual materials, such as computers, players, projectors, interactive boards, and the use of all these tools significantly increases the interest of students in the lesson, and also helps to directly maintain interest in the studied subject. But it should be remembered that these tools are not the main, but additional in language teaching and can never replace the teacher. Motivation is one of the main factors determining the success of learning a foreign language. This is the main motivation to start learning a foreign language, and then the determination to endure and endure the long and boring hours of the difficult learning process. Without enough desire, motivation and, of course, motivation, even the best students will not always achieve their long-term goals. Encouraging students to learn a foreign language is a complex task that requires a lot of effort from the student and a creative approach from the teacher. Unmotivated students cannot learn effectively. They do not remember information for a long time; they are not involved in the language learning process. A student can be unenthusiastic for many reasons: he is not interested in this subject and may think that he will not need it in the future. Some may not be interested in the teacher's methods or may be distracted by external factors.

Some students may simply have learning difficulties and require special attention. Motivated students enjoy learning and participating in school life. Some students are self-motivated by their love of learning. But even with students who lack intrinsic motivation, a good teacher can make learning fun, engaging, and inspiring them to reach their full potential.

In the field of English language learning and teaching, there is a debate about the role of motivation in language learning, and therefore the use of motivation in language learning and teaching has been the subject of considerable debate among experts. But scientists agree that motivation is very important for language learning and plays a key role in learning effectiveness.

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